

Building with Nature: Bamboo and Stone Masonry for Sustainable and Resilient Structures in Nepal

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Abstract

Rural Nepal faces significant challenges in achieving safe and resilient construction due to economic constraints and limited access to engineered materials. Locally available resources, such as stone and soil for masonry, and bamboo, have historically provided affordable, culturally significant, and environmentally sustainable solutions. Stone masonry with mud mortar (SMM) remains widely used for homes, temples, and community buildings, yet these structures often lack scientifically validated design codes and guidelines, leaving them vulnerable to seismic hazards. Similarly, bamboo, with its high strength-to-weight ratio and renewability, has been extensively used in informal construction, but standardized codal and design provision which includes joint systems and mechanical performance data are scarce.

This keynote will explore the potential of bamboo and stone masonry as sustainable and resilient building materials in Nepal, highlighting recent ongoing experimental and numerical research. The practical strategies for enhancing the mechanical performance, durability, and seismic resilience of these traditional materials while maintaining cultural compatibility and affordability will be discussed.

Additionally, the talk will introduce the Applied Element Method (AEM) as a powerful computational tool for simulating the behavior of complex structures under seismic loading. Coupled with structural health monitoring using vibration data, AEM allows for real-time assessment of building performance, identification of vulnerabilities, and informed decision-making for repair and strengthening interventions.

By bridging traditional knowledge with modern engineering techniques, this presentation aims to provide a roadmap for evidence-based, context-appropriate, and low-cost approaches to sustainable construction in Nepal. The talk will benefit engineers, architects, policymakers, and researchers seeking to advance resilient infrastructure using locally available, environmentally friendly materials.

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